

HOZIRGI KUNDA RAQAMLI TA'LIMNING AHAMIYATI

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O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti, Tarjimonlik fakulteti, Ingliz tili tarjima nazariyasi kafedra katta o'qituvchisi; O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari universiteti, Tarjimonlik fakulteti, Ingliz tili tarjima nazariyasi 4 kurs talabasi

Annotatsiya:

Raqamli ta'lim bu - o'quv jarayonini yaxshilash va osonlashtirish uchun raqamli texnologiyalar va vositalardan foydalanishdir. U elektron ta'lim, onlayn kurslar, virtual sinflar, ta'lim dasturlari va interaktiv multimedia resurslari kabi texnologiya vositasida o'qitishning turli shakllarini o'z ichiga oladi. Raqamli ta'lim ko'plab afzalliklari mavjud bo'lib, jumladan, keng foydalanish imkoniyati va moslashuvchanligi, shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim tajribasi va istalgan vaqtda istalgan joydan o'quv materiallari va resurslariga kirish imkoniyati. U videolar, interaktiv viktorinalar va virtual simulyatsiyalar kabi multimedia elementlarini birlashtirishga imkon beradi, bu esa ma'lumotni jalb qilish, tushunish va saqlashni kuchaytiradi. Bundan tashqari, raqamli ta'lim hamkorlikda o'rganish, global aloqalar va raqamli savodxonlik ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun imkoniyatlar beradi. O'qituvchilar interaktiv va qiziqarli ta'lim tajribasini yaratish, muloqot va hamkorlikni osonlashtirish, talabalar taraqqiyotini kuzatish va fikr-mulohazalarni taqdim etish va o'quv natijalarini kuzatish uchun raqamli vositalar va platformalardan foydalanishlari mumkin. Shuningdek, u umrbod ta'lim olish, kasbiy rivojlanish va turli fanlar bo'yicha yangi ko'nikmalarni egallash uchun keng yo'l ochadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Elektron ta'lim, onlayn ta'lim, masofaviy ta'lim, aralash ta'lim, gibril, edtech, MOOC, gamifikatsiya, virtual haqiqat (VR), sun'iy intellekt (AI), shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim

Аннотация:

Цифровое образование подразумевает использование цифровых технологий и инструментов для улучшения и облегчения процесса обучения. Оно включает в себя различные формы обучения с использованием технологий, такие как электронное обучение, онлайн-курсы, виртуальные классы, образовательные приложения и интерактивные мультимедийные ресурсы. Цифровое образование предлагает множество преимуществ, включая повышенную доступность и гибкость, персонализированный опыт обучения, а также возможность доступа к образовательным материалам и ресурсам из любого места и в любое время. Он позволяет интегрировать мультимедийные элементы, такие как видео, интерактивные викторины и виртуальные симуляции, что может повысить вовлеченность, понимание и сохранение информации. Более того, цифровое образование предоставляет возможности для совместного обучения, глобальных связей и развития навыков цифровой грамотности. Преподаватели могут использовать цифровые инструменты и платформы для создания интерактивного и увлекательного обучения, облегчения общения и сотрудничества, отслеживания прогресса учащихся и предоставления обратной связи, а также отслеживания результатов обучения. Это также открывает возможности для непрерывного обучения,

профессионального развития и приобретения новых навыков в различных дисциплинах.

Ключевые слова: Электронное обучение, онлайн-обучение, дистанционное образование, смешанное обучение, гибридное обучение, образовательные технологии, MOOK, геймификация, виртуальная реальность (VR), искусственный интеллект (ИИ), персонализированное обучение.

Annotation:

Digital education refers to the use of digital technologies and tools to enhance and facilitate the learning process. It encompasses various forms of technology-mediated learning, such as e-learning, online courses, virtual classrooms, educational apps, and interactive multimedia resources. Digital education offers numerous benefits, including increased accessibility and flexibility, personalized learning experiences, and the ability to access educational materials and resources from anywhere at any time. It allows for the integration of multimedia elements, such as videos, interactive quizzes, and virtual simulations, which can enhance engagement, understanding, and retention of information. Moreover, digital education provides opportunities for collaborative learning, global connections, and the development of digital literacy skills. Educators can leverage digital tools and platforms to create interactive and engaging learning experiences, facilitate communication and collaboration, monitor student progress and provide feedback, and track learning outcomes. It also opens up avenues for lifelong learning, professional development, and the acquisition of new skills in various disciplines.

Key words: E-learning, online learning, distance education, blended learning, hybrid, edtech, MOOC, gamification, virtual reality (VR), artificial intelligence (AI), personalized learning.

Digital education refers to the use of digital technologies or resources to support and enhance teaching and learning processes. Right now, digital education has become more important than ever due to the COVID-19 pandemic, as it enables students and teachers to continue their educational activities remotely. It includes various online platforms, educational apps, virtual classrooms, video conferencing tools, and other digital resources that facilitate interactive and engaging learning experiences. Digital education allows for personalized learning, access to a vast amount of educational content, collaboration among students, and the development of essential digital skills. Digital education is of utmost importance in today's world for several reasons.

Enhancing access to education: Digital education bridges the gap between privileged and underprivileged communities by providing access to quality education materials and resources. It allows students from all backgrounds to access educational content, regardless of their geographical location or financial constraints.

Enabling personalized learning: Digital education provides opportunities for personalized learning, allowing students to learn at their own pace and according to their individual needs and preferences. This flexibility helps students to understand concepts better and enhances their overall learning experience.

Fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills: Digital education encourages students to engage in interactive learning experiences that promote critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Through various online platforms and tools, students can actively participate in discussions, analyze information, and develop their analytical abilities.

Preparing students for the future workforce: In an increasingly digital world, digital literacy and skills are essential for career success. Digital education equips students with the necessary technical skills and knowledge required in today's job market. It prepares them to adapt to new technologies and work effectively in digital environments.

Enhancing collaboration and global connectivity: Digital education enables students to collaborate with peers and experts from around the world. It breaks down the barriers of distance and facilitates virtual connections, allowing students to learn from diverse perspectives and cultures.

Promoting lifelong learning: Digital education encourages lifelong learning by providing various online courses, webinars, and resources that are accessible to individuals of all ages. It promotes continuous skill development and empowers individuals to stay updated with the latest knowledge and trends.

Digital education is the use of digital technologies and resources to facilitate and enhance teaching, learning, and educational experiences. It encompasses a wide range of tools, platforms, and digital resources, including online learning platforms, educational apps, multimedia content, virtual classrooms, video conferencing tools, and more. Digital education allows for remote learning, personalized learning experiences, collaborative learning, and the development of essential digital skills. It provides flexibility in terms of time and location, making education more accessible and inclusive. With digital education, learners can engage with educational content in interactive and immersive ways, fostering a deeper understanding and higher level of engagement. It also enables continuous learning and professional development beyond traditional educational institutions. Digital education plays a crucial role in modern education, preparing learners for the digital age and equipping them with the skills they need to thrive in a rapidly evolving world.

The main purpose of digital education now is to provide accessible and flexible learning opportunities for individuals of all ages and backgrounds. It aims to leverage technology to deliver educational content, facilitate interactive learning experiences, and enhance skills development. Digital education helps overcome geographical barriers, promotes lifelong learning, fosters digital literacy, and prepares individuals for the evolving job market in the digital age.

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